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Editor-in-Chief's Desk

Dear Esteemed Professors and Researchers,

We often hear about your aspirations to publish articles in international journals. Inspired by your academic potential, we are pleased to announce the launch of Econoscitech-Integration, an international scientific journal specializing in socio-economics, science and technology, and innovation. Our journal is committed to fostering collaborative ties with prominent research centers across Central Asia and Europe, promoting the exchange of new knowledge and innovations.

Through Econoscitech-Integration, we aim to bring valuable research, analyses, and practical insights focused on the socio-economic development of our country to a wide audience. Here, we provide an opportunity to address issues in economics, technology, innovation, and social sciences through modern scientific approaches and to implement them in practice. The research published in our journal covers not only theoretical knowledge but also addresses relevant and impactful practical topics.

If you have innovative ideas in fields such as economics, engineering, education, tourism, or other critical areas, and wish to explore solutions, we invite you to collaborate with us. We value every article submitted, recognizing its importance for societal and national development, and we approach each submission with dedicated attention.

Zufarova Nozima Gulamiddinovna
DSc., Dean of Tourism Faculty, TSUE

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FOOD SECURITY PROBLEMS

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Annotation: This article examines the issues of ensuring the population of our country has access to high-quality food products and guaranteeing food safety. It outlines the main directions and strategies for achieving these goals, with a focus on sustainability and addressing global challenges.

Key Words: Food security, agricultural products, environmentally clean products, stability, global population, hunger, production output.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматриваются вопросы обеспечения населения нашей страны качественными продуктами питания и гарантирования продовольственной безопасности. Описаны основные направления и стратегии достижения этих целей с учетом устойчивого развития и глобальных вызовов.

Ключевые слова: Продовольственная безопасность, сельскохозяйственная продукция, экологически чистые продукты, стабильность, мировое население, голод, объем производства.

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada mamlakatimiz aholisini sifatli oziq-ovqat mahsulotlari bilan ta'minlash va oziq-ovqat xavfsizligini kafolatlash masalalari ko'rib chiqilgan. Ushbu maqsadlarga erishish yo'llari va strategiyalari barqarorlik hamda global muammolarni hisobga olgan holda yoritib berilgan.

Tayanch iboralar: Oziq-ovqat xavfsizligi, qishloq xo'jaligi mahsulotlari, ekologik toza mahsulotlar, barqarorlik, global aholi soni, ocharchilik, ishlab chiqarish hajmi.

1. INTRODUCTION.

It is known that food products are essential for the survival and development of the human organism. In recent years, the sharp changes in the global climate, deterioration of ecological conditions, and increasing demographic indicators worldwide have led to a growing demand for food products and their safety.

The global population growth not only impacts food production but also has a serious socio-economic effect. Food safety is a broad concept that primarily implies the independence of a state from relying on other countries for food products. Additionally, it involves ensuring that the population is sufficiently provided with consumption goods in accordance with physiological standards.

In recent years, climate changes have increasingly resulted in higher soil salinity. The structure of soils has also been changing. Despite efforts by developed and developing countries to improve agricultural activities and increase food production, the growth in food production remains

behind the rate of population growth. In countries where favorable conditions for the development of agriculture do not exist, this issue is becoming increasingly problematic.

2.LITERATURE REVIEW.

According to information from the United Nations Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) and the World Health Organization (WHO), currently, over 840 million people worldwide—approximately one in eight—do not have enough to eat. Recent studies indicate that 30% of the global population suffers from malnutrition due to a lack of essential trace elements and vitamins. Hunger has been categorized as "serious" or "alarming" in 52 countries. The majority of those suffering from hunger—over 520 million people—are in Asia.

The rapid growth of the population, combined with limited food production capabilities, has made the provision of high-quality food a major issue for many countries.

In the years of independence, the Republic of Uzbekistan has achieved significant progress in the field of agriculture. For instance, the production of agricultural products has doubled in size.

3.RESEARCH AND METHODOLOGY.

The research methodology focuses on analyzing the current state of food security in our country through a multidisciplinary approach. Data collection involved statistical analysis of agricultural production outputs, market trends, and environmental factors affecting food quality. Comparative analysis was employed to evaluate global food security standards and identify best practices. A qualitative approach was used to assess the socioeconomic factors influencing food accessibility, while case studies from countries with successful food security models were reviewed to propose actionable strategies for improvement.

4.ANALYSIS AND RESULTS.

In our country, ensuring food security is one of the key directions for safeguarding citizens' health, improving their quality of life, stabilizing the socio-economic situation, fostering sustainable development, and preserving national security and independence. In this regard, the Republic is undertaking purposeful and consistent measures to ensure the stable provision of high-quality food products for the population and to support agricultural producers.

On February 7, 2017, the President of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Miromonovich Mirziyoyev, signed the "Action Strategy on Five Priority Areas of Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017–2021." This decree highlighted food security as a priority in the context of economic development and liberalization. The document emphasized the deepening of structural changes, consistent development of agricultural production, strengthening of national food security, expansion of ecological clean product output, and a significant increase in the export potential of the agricultural sector.

In the President's 2019 Address to the Oliy Majlis on priority tasks, the goal of reforms in agriculture was defined as achieving economic benefits while ensuring food security and improving the well-being of the population. In line with this vision, the Cabinet of Ministers adopted the decision to approve the "National Program for Ensuring Food Security in the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2019–2024." The implementation of this decision continues to contribute to ensuring food security through a comprehensive program of measures.

The following main directions for ensuring food security in Uzbekistan have been defined: Improving the legal and institutional framework for food security. Rational use of land and water resources allocated for agriculture. Stable development of domestic production of key agricultural and food products, including raw materials. Sustainable development of livestock, poultry, and fisheries, increasing production volumes, and strengthening the food supply base. Improving the infrastructure for the production of agricultural and food products. Ensuring the safety and quality of food products. Expanding economic opportunities for all population groups to access food products. Establishing and controlling state mechanisms to ensure food security.

According to experts, in January–September 2022, the total volume of agriculture, forestry, and fishery production and services amounted to 248.6 trillion soums, which is a 3.6% increase compared to the same period in 2021.

- **Vegetables:** 8 million tons (leading production segment).
- **Grain products:** 6.7 million tons.
- **Potatoes:** 2.6 million tons.
- **Oilseed crops:** 1.6 million tons.
- **Fruits and berries:** 2.2 million tons.
- **Grapes:** 1.4 million tons.

The ongoing reforms in Uzbekistan aim to ensure the sustainable development of the fruit and vegetable farming sector over the long term. Increasing the efficiency of this network ensures the population's demand for food products is met, food safety is maintained, exports are expanded, and better living conditions for citizens are created.

Providing the population with sufficient high-quality food is a fundamental component of food security. Meeting the population's needs for key food products while maintaining a balance between price and quality, and guaranteeing food safety through state mechanisms, remains one of the key conditions for socio-economic development.

5.CONCLUSION.

Ensuring food security requires a multifaceted approach that includes increasing agricultural productivity, promoting environmentally sustainable practices, and addressing socioeconomic barriers to food access. This study highlights the need for integrated efforts among stakeholders to establish a stable and resilient food system. Implementing the recommended strategies will not only improve the availability of high-quality food products but also contribute to long-term national and global food security goals.

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